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DESIGNING A PLEASANT NEW RENTAL BICYCLE SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

This study is concerned with improving the current rental bicycle system in Kish Island. Bicycle riding is one of the attractions of Kish and a rental bicycle system is available in this island. However, it seems this system has some shortcomings and needs improvements. In order to obtain the design parameters, Kansei Engineering method was employed. Forty people were asked to explain their expectations of the system. One hundred and ten Kansei words were collected and reduced to four higher-level words by employing "Seven Point Scale Rating". For obtaining the system properties, a benchmark table was prepared and for identifying the design database, a trend board was created. Regarding the design parameters, several concepts were generated and one concept was developed. Thirty users were selected to evaluate the new concept in a showroom. Due to the users' satisfaction, it was concluded that the new concept could meet the users' expectations.

Keywords: Rental Bicycle System, Bicycle rack, Kansei Engineering.

INTRODUCTION

Developing new products requires some knowledge regarding the effects of product on its customers. Obviously, all manufacturers and service providers intend to design systems in a way that can evoke a positive impact on users and encourage them to use the system. For this aim combination of sensing, intellectual, emotional, social, behavioral and spiritual experiences are involved. To attain a profound affection, products and services should

satisfy all potential users' needs and demands (Dahlgard et al, 2008). If the system performance meets the expectations, the user would be satisfied. If the system performance exceeds expectations, the user would be highly satisfied or delighted and when system features provide high satisfaction, the product and service become familiar to the user (Kankainen, 2003).

People's emotions enrich virtually all of their moments with either a pleasant or an unpleasant quality. Emotional responses can incite users to select a particular product or service and may have a considerable influence on their purchase decisions (Desmet, 2004). Impressions of a product are important for the decision of purchasing it or not. It means people purchase the product, which 'feels' better, so product development probably goes towards integration of emotional values in products. Therefore, actions and interactions with many systems including social-sharing system can be conducted emotionally (Schutte, 2005). Biking networks in big cities play an important role to increase mobility choices, improve air quality and reduce congestion. The basic idea of these systems is sustainable transportation (Midgley, 2009) by encouraging people to ride bicycle and use the sharing-system. Employing emotional aspects could be practical in determining the attributes and designing a suitable system.

Rental bicycle system in Kish Island is launched to encourage people to bike. Bicycle riding is one of the attractions of Kish Island that is known as an entertainment and an enjoyable sport. Also it is beneficial to the environmental goals and attracts tourists. Despite of the attraction of the rental bicycle system, the current system has some

weaknesses, which have led to the users' dissatisfaction. Therefore, further investigation was needed and a study was carried out.

DEVELOPING A NEW RENTAL BICYCLE SYSTEM

The study was performed in three phases. In first phase, the shortcomings of the available rental bicycle system were identified. In second phase, the users' feelings and demands were captured and the design parameters for designing a new, pleasant rental bicycle system were obtained. In last phase, newly designed bicycle rack and service were evaluated by Kansei Engineering method.

PHASE ONE: CLARIFYING THE PROBLEMS

To find out the disadvantages of the existing rental bicycle system, its users and context of use were identified.

Kish Island is located in Persian Gulf. It is a small and tropical island with high humidity level (relative humidity is 50-60 percent) and high temperature.

The island's surface is flat, with no mountains or high hills. This topography feature makes Kish Island a suitable place for bicycle riding. It has a 51km bike lane along the beach. This lane is stretched all around the island and the cyclists can enjoy the beautiful nature during cycling. The beautiful Kish Island is a safe, peaceful and clean zone. It is an excellent travel destination for the families. The main visions of Kish Free Zone Organization are developing environmental aspects and tourism in Kish Island. Rental bicycle system can play an important role to satisfy both visions by encouraging people to use the rental bicycles. Furthermore, Kish Island is the only place in Iran that women are allowed to ride the bicycle. Cycling is a popular sport in Kish and public cycling plans are arranged by Kish Free Zone Organization in order to encourage people to cycle. Nineteen bicycle stations have been launched all around the island for renting bicycles. Each station is controlled by an operator but these stations are not functionally connected together (Figure 1).

Figure 1. A bicycle station in Kish Island

To obtain the best results, it is important to identify the end users and other stakeholders who may be impacted by the system (Maguire, 2001). In Kish, most of the end users are the Iranian tourists who visit this island. Mostly, the journey time of Kish tourists lasts 3 to 5 days. The users are 8 to 70 years of age. The most important stakeholders are the bicycle stations' operators who are responsible for controlling and managing the stations and rental service.

To find out the shortcomings of the available system and improve it, it is necessary to explore users' characteristics and their interactions with the system. For this aim, the system was tried personally and forty users were observed and interviewed. As a result, the steps of renting the bicycle were realized as follow (Figure 2):

Step1. User walks to the bicycle station.

Step2. User gives his/her identification card to the operator. The operator writes user's name and the time that the bicycle is rented.

Step3. User chooses a bicycle and removes it.

Step4. User starts the journey by rental bicycle.

When the user's journey finishes, the rental bicycle is returned to the same station. As Figure 3 shows, the steps of returning the rental bicycle are as follow:

Step1. User rides to the bicycle station.

Step2. User gets off the bicycle at the station.

Step3. User parks the bicycle in an empty rack.

Step4. User goes toward the operator. The operator identifies the renting time and calculates the cost. User pays the money to the operator and the operator returns user's ID card.

Step5. User leaves the station.

Figure 2. User's actions to rent the bicycle from the available rental system

Figure 3. User's actions to return the rental bicycle to the available rental system

Twenty men and twenty women were interviewed. These users were asked to explain their opinions about the available system which they had experienced. They were also asked to explain their feelings and ideas about the ideal bike-sharing system. The results were gathered and analyzed. According to the results, the weaknesses were related to bicycle shelters, bicycle racks and renting service. The most important disadvantages were classified as below:

- Bicycle racks have sharp edges that make them unsafe.
- Bicycle racks are made of steel tubes which make them very hot in summer days. Also, steel is not corrosion resistant and suitable to be used in humid climate.
- Bicycle must be returned to the station which had been rented from. So the bicycle stations are not functionally connected to each other.

- ID cards are taken to guarantee returning the rental bicycles, while sometimes cyclists need to use their identification card.
- The gap between the racks is not wide enough to remove and park the bicycles.
- Fastening the bicycles by chain and lock to the racks is difficult and old fashioned.

PHASE TWO: IDENTIFYING THE DESIGN PARAMETERS

To improve understanding of the nature of products and its emotional impact on the users and translate them into actual product design solutions, Kansei Engineering method was employed. This method includes some steps to identify the project domain, span the semantic space and product properties, synthesize, test of validity and build the model (Schutte, 2002).

After finding the shortcomings of the bicycle rental system and the attributes that people expect from such a system, Kansei Engineering method was employed. Kansei Engineering is a practical method for product development, which is able to capture the users' expectations as words and translate them into concrete product design (Schutte, 2005). The ideas and preferences were translated into Kansei words. In order to get a complete selection of words, available sources such as internet, sport magazines, technical manuals and books were explored. Finally one hundred and ten words were collected. To reduce the number of Kansei words, "Seven-point scale rating" was used. Figure 4 shows the example of Seven-point scale rating questionnaire.

Figure 4. Seven-point scale rating questionnaire

Forty expert users were asked to rate the importance of each Kansei word from one to seven scales (from "Not at all" to "Very much"). Regarding the final scores, the number of Kansei words was reduced to twenty one words (Table 1).

Higher-level word	Kansei word	Bicycle rack and rental service properties	Higher-level word	Kansei word	Bicycle rack and rental service properties
Attractive	Attractive	user-friendly colors in rack's body, curved lines and circular shapes in rack's form	Safe	Safe cycling	GPS system
				Anti-theft	
Comfortable	Connected stations	Local Area Connection (LAN)		Safe for users	Standard dimensions (97cm in height, 20cm in width, 20cm in depth)
				Tough structure	Rough and strong material like steel tubes for structure of the rack
	Practical for all the users	Not taking the ID cards		Enough racks (safe for bicycle)	Increasing the number of racks (between 30 and 50)
	Familiar mechanism	Shaft and coin mechanism to lock and unlock the bicycle in the rack, similar to mechanism of coin trolley and coin computer game.		Practical installation (to access and park the bicycle)	Rational spaces or installation angels of racks in each row (The distance between the racks is 65cm and the installation angle is 60 degree)
	Automatic mechanism (for locking and unlocking)				
Easy to use	Easy performance (usable for every user even children and old people)	Improvable		Access points are needed	
Safe	Possible to prepare equipment (helmet, bicycle coin, bicycle basket and key map)				Operator is needed
		Corrosion resistance		Corrosion resistance material like aluminum sheets for outer body and hot-galvanized steel tubes for inner structure of the rack	
	Usable to park every size of bicycles	Standard dimensions for racks	Recyclable	Recyclable materials (Aluminum and steel are both recyclable)	
	Reliable to park and fasten every size of bicycles	Locking the bicycle in specific part in the rack by shaft	Sustainable service	Sustainable system and materials	
	Safe for bicycle	Shaft and coin mechanism to lock and unlock the bicycle in the rack			
Durable					

Table 1. Kansei words and new rental bicycle system properties

According to their affinity, the words were categorized in four groups. For each group a representative was chosen as a higher-level Kansei word. As Table 1 shows “Comfortable”, “Attractive”, “Safe” and “Durable” are the higher-level Kansei words.

To span the space of properties, a collection of selected product properties relevant to the semantic space (Kansei words) was prepared by benchmark table. For this aim, different sources such as existing products, experts' suggestions and possible technical solutions were used (Table 1).

To provide the design database, some design elements like color variations, forms and textures were investigated by Conjoint Trend Analysis (CTA). In order to perform CTA method, Iranian people's trends were identified and the images of Iranian people's amusements, favorite sports and places were collected. Also the images of cyclists' favorite equipments were gathered. All of this information was presented in a Trend Board (Figure 5). The forms, textures and colors of Trend Board were determined and analyzed. The most repetitive elements were defined as the design database to generate new concepts. These elements were presented as the CTA results (Figure 6). As figure 6 shows, curved lines and circular forms, soft and glossy textures and colors such as orange, red, yellow, blue, green, white, black and grey were identified as the design database.

Figure 6. The CTA results

In the synthesis step, regarding the Kansei words, collected properties and design database, several concepts were generated for rental service and bicycle rack. Due to the design limitations such as users' ability, bicycles attributes, and technical and environmental considerations, one rental service and one new bicycle rack concept were selected.

The model of the rack concept was built which is shown in Figure 7. The new rack dimensions are 97cm in height, 20cm in width and 20cm in depth. Depending on the location of each bicycle station, the racks are installed in single rows or double rows. They are installed at 60 degree angle in each row. The distance between the racks is 65cm. The rack is made of aluminum sheets (outer body) and hot-galvanized steel tubes (inner structure).

The structure of the new rack has a hole which is 70cm in height, 7.5cm in width and 20cm in depth. The lock-unlock mechanism of the rack is performed by coin and shaft system which is easy to use even for children and old users.

To park and lock the bicycle, it is positioned in the rack's hole. Due to the width of the hole, half of the bicycle wheel can be placed in the rack's hole and the whole body of the bicycle can be stabled by the rack. Then the bicycle rime is sensed by a sensor which is placed in the hole. After sensing, the shaft which is 3cm in length, moves and locks the wheel. After locking the bicycle, coin drops out of the rack and user can pick that and return it to the operator. This shows that the bicycle has been parked successfully in the rack.

To release the bicycle from the rack, the coin should be fallen in rack. By falling the coin the shaft moves and bicycle is released.

According to the design database, the new rack has curved shapes with orange fish pattern which contributes to its context in Kish Island (Figure 7).

Figure 5. Trend Board of people's favorites in Kish Island

Figure 7. New concept for bicycle rack

After building the rack model, user's interactions with the new system for renting and returning the bicycle, were presented in two Storyboards (Figure 8 and 9). As Figure 8 shows, interaction with new rental bicycle system for renting the bicycle includes following actions:

- Step1. User moves to the bicycle station.
 - Step2. User moves to the operator's place at the station.
 - Step3. User shows his/her identification card to the operator.
 - Step4. User can borrow additional equipment such as helmet, bicycle basket, bicycle lock and key map.
 - Step5. Operator inserts the user's identification, list of borrowed equipment, date and time to the computer which is connected to other stations' computers by LAN (Local Area Connection).
 - Step6. Operator gives the bicycle coin and equipment to the user.
 - Step7. User moves to the bicycle racks and chooses a bicycle.
 - Step8. User drops the bicycle coin into the rack.
 - Step9. After dropping the coin, the shaft which had locked the bicycle rim and tire, moves into the rack (shaft's hole) and bicycle can be released.
 - Step10. User removes the bicycle and rides it.
- The rental bicycles can be rented at one station and either returned there or to other stations.

Figure 8. User's actions to rent the bicycle from the new rental system

- According to Figure 9, the steps of returning a rental bicycle to the new rental system are as follow:
- Step1. The cyclist rides to any bicycle station.
 - Step2. At the station, the cyclist gets off the bicycle.
 - Step3. User parks the bicycle in an empty bicycle rack.
 - Step4. After placing the bicycle in the rack, the bicycle rim is sensed by the rack's sensor.
 - Step5. While the bicycle is sensing, the shaft gets out of the rack (shaft's hole) and locks the rim and tire.
 - Step6. After locking, the bicycle coin drops out of the rack.
 - Step7. User picks the bicycle coin and additional equipment.
 - Step8. User moves to the operator's place, shows the identification card and returns the bicycle coin and borrowed equipment to the operator.
 - Step9. Operator opens the user's profile in the computer. Regarding the information which has been registered in the user's profile the operator checks out the time and list of borrowed equipment. Then he calculates the cost.
 - Step10. User pays the money and leaves the station.

Figure 9. User's actions to return the rental bicycle to the new system

PHASE THREE: EVALUATING THE NEWLY DEVELOPED CONCEPT

The aim of this phase is evaluating the new rental system concept. In order to evaluate the new concept, a showroom was prepared. The new rack model and Storyboards were presented in the showroom to describe the system (Figure 7, 8 and 9). Then thirty people, fifteen women and fifteen men who were selected randomly from the users of rental bicycle system in Kish Island, were asked to evaluate the new rental system concept. Evaluation was carried out regarding the higher-level Kansei words by Seven-point scale rating questionnaire (Figure 4). In this questionnaire, minimum relationship between each higher-level Kansei word and the new rental system was indicated by 'one' and maximum relationship was indicated by 'seven'. Also the participants' reactions and behaviors were observed closely when they were interacting with the model of the rack and storyboards.

The results of the seven-point scale rating questionnaires were analyzed by Excel software to obtain the final scores for each higher-level Kansei word. The final scores are presented in Figure 10. These results show how much the relationship between the higher-level Kansei words and the attributes of the new rental bicycle system is strong

in users' opinion. For evaluating, the scores between seven to six were considered as very strong, six to five as strong, five to four as medium, four to three as weak, three to two as very weak and two to one as rare relationships. As figure 10 shows, Attractive and Comfortable have got the highest scores (6.5 out of 7) which means there is a very strong relationship between these Kansei words and the new system. Also the Figure shows that users have felt strong relationship (5.8 and 5.5 out of 7) between the concept and Safe and Durable words.

Figure 10. Final scores of higher-level Kansei words in new rental bicycle system

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The successful design evokes positive impacts on potential users, encourages them to use the system and causes satisfaction of use.

Some systems are well-equipped but have no attraction to persuade users to interact with them. In order to design an efficient product or system, it is necessary to understand the users' needs and expectations.

Public-sharing systems play important roles to provide safety, health and attraction.

Bicycle riding is one of the amusements that encourage Iranian people to visit Kish and most of tourists are interested in renting the bicycle.

In the available rental system, the necessity of leaving ID cards for renting the bicycles and the obligation of returning the bicycles to the origin station (which the bicycle is rented from), make the system impractical and unattractive. Also there are some shortcomings with racks and chains. Therefore, there is a need to design a new pleasant rental system. In this study, Kansei Engineering was employed as an emotional method to add emotional attractions and user-friendly attributes to the system. This can encourage people to use the rental system.

New system was designed based on the people's words and trends and has many advantages compared with the available system. For instance, the roles of the operators are changed and improved. Users directly interact with the racks. Replacing the chains with Coins and shaft system in new racks, makes the rental service safe and secure. All stations are functionally connected by LAN and it makes the system more practical, so users don't need to return to the origin station for taking back their ID cards and returning the rental bicycle. In new system, the cost is calculated easily and correctly.

The results of evaluating the new concept by Kansei Engineering method indicate that attributes of the new system have strong relationships with people's expectations and demands. Users feel that the new rack is attractive and comfortable for interacting. Also, regarding the process of use, they feel safe and secure. In the new rental system, operators are more comfortable and their bicycles are safe. In addition, the goals of making Kish Island more attractive and green are achieved by new system.

Finally it was concluded that Kansei Engineering is a suitable method for this study.

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